

A Relationship Between Band Widths in Solution and in Gas Phase

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The width of a band in solution can be predicted from a knowledge of the width in the gas phase using the derived semi-empirical relationship

$$\Delta y_{\frac{1}{2}(s)} = \frac{1.63 \times 10^{10}}{PLy_g} \ln (T_o/T) y_{\max} \Delta y_{\frac{1}{2}(g)} \frac{(n+2)^2}{n} + 2.5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$$

where $\Delta y_{\frac{1}{2}(s)}$ is the solution half-band width, $\Delta y_{\frac{1}{2}(g)}$ the gas half-band width, P the gas pressure, L the cell thickness, y_g the gas frequency, $\ln (T_o/T) y_{\max}$ the gas absorbance at maximum absorption and n the refractive index of the solvent. Published measurements of the C—H stretching vibration band of acetylene in various solvents have been examined to test the proposed relationship which has been found to fit the data in solvents of low polarity well.

Recently Cole and Mitchell¹ pointed out the non-existence of any theory to date to predict quantitatively the width of a band in solution from a knowledge of the band width in the gas phase. A quantitative relationship can however, be obtained basing ideas on existing theories and experimental relationship. A semi-empirical treatment for the derivation of the relationship is presented in this paper and applied with reasonable success to the C—H stretching vibration band.

Many workers such as Chako², Polo and Wilson³ and Van Kranendonk⁴ derived an expression connecting the solution intensity, A_s , and the gas phase intensity, A_g , of a vibration band in the form

$$A_s / A_g = (n^2 + 2)^2 / 9n \quad \dots (1)$$

where n is the refractive index of the solvent. It has been assumed that the refractive indices of the solvent and the solution remain equal. The Debye or Lornetz treatment of electric field equation for a dielectric was used in Chako's treatment while Polo and Wilson used the Onsager reaction field concepts. Van Kranendonk referred to two types of absorption, (a) the true induced absorption due to the short range intermolecular force (b) the apparent induced absorption due to the relatively long range dipole-dipole interactions. Although the treatments hold for the interaction of a band which is fairly polar, substitution of $e = n^2$ as Buckingham⁷ has shown makes the equation valid for non polar non rigid molecules as the dipole moment used results from the molecular vibrations.

Similar other equations used are those due to Hirota⁵ viz.,

$$A_s/A_g = [(n^2+2)(2D+1)/3(2D+n^2)]^2 \quad \dots (2)$$

who obtained solution to gas intensity ratio for fundamentals and overtones where D is the dielectric constant of the solvent, and Buckingham^{1,6,7} who obtained the ratio for polar and polarizable diatomic molecules viz.,

$$A_s/A_g = \left[\frac{9n^2}{(n^2+2)(2n^2+1)} \right] \left[1 + C'_D \frac{D-1}{2D+1} + C'_n \frac{n^2-1}{2n^2+1} \right] \quad \dots (2a)$$

The observed solution intensity could be related to that of the frequency shift Δy using Bauer-Magat formula⁸ and Polo-Wilson equation^{9,11}. Bauer and Magat derived the equation

$$\Delta y/y_g = \left(\frac{n-1}{2n^2+1} \right) \left(\frac{1}{4\pi^2 a^3 y_g^2} \right) \left(\frac{\delta\mu}{\delta Q} \right)^2 \quad \dots (3)$$

where a is the cavity radius, considering a liquid molecule as an elementary point-like dipole surrounded by a sphere of a cavity with a dielectric constant, applicable for non polar solvent in line with Onsager's theory¹⁰ for the polarization of dipolar liquids in a constant electric field. The limitations of this equation as has been shown by Jorseen and Lascombe⁹ are (a) that smaller shifts are observed for CFCl_3 , than predicted from the refractive indices and (b) that for small values of cavity radius of 1 to 1.5 Å the equation does not explain the observed shifts for many compounds.

Polo and Wilson substantiated the multiplicative effect, caused by the induced absorption by a surrounding dielectric upon the transitory dipole moment of intermolecular origin of medium intensity in liquids, solids, and in solutions formed from liquids and solids because of molecular interaction, that also governs the intensity of intrinsic absorption, with their equation

$$A_s = \left(\frac{n^2+2}{3} \right)^2 \left(\frac{N\pi}{3cn} \right) \left(\frac{\delta\mu}{\delta Q} \right)^2 \quad \dots (4)$$

where N is the number of molecules per cc (2.68×10^{19}), c is the velocity of light (3×10^{10} cm sec⁻¹), $[(n^2+2)/3n^2]^2$ and $(2n^2+1)/(n^2-1)$ are the refractive index factors, nearly equal to 1.3 and 4.9 respectively. The value of the cavity radius ranges from 2.3 to 3 Å^{12,13}: It can be derived from the empirical equation

$$\frac{4\pi a^3}{3} N = 0.74 V_m$$

where V_m is the molar volume. The average value of 2.65 Å in conformity with van Ostenburg's value¹⁴ has been used in this work.

From equations (3) and (4) on rearrangement, we have the relation between the solution intensity and frequency shift as

$$A_s = \left(\frac{n^2+2}{3n^2} \right)^2 \left(\frac{2n^2+1}{n^2-1} \right) \left(\frac{4\pi^3 a^3 N y_g}{3c} \right) \Delta y \quad \dots (5)$$

For reasonable values of refractive index, the solution intensity is predicted to be proportional to the frequency shift.

It has further been experimentally observed¹⁵ that the solution frequency shift of a fundamental band is related to $\Delta y_{\ddagger(s)}$ according to the equation,

$$\Delta y_{\ddagger(s)} = 0.72\Delta y + 2.5 \text{ cm}^{-1} \quad \dots (6)$$

Huggins and Pimental obtained the empirical relation from a study of the hydrogen bonding effect of the O-H stretching frequency in various solvents.

From the measurement of absolute intensities of infrared bands in liquids Ramsay¹⁶ developed a method for determining the intensity of a band from a knowledge of its half band width. Assuming the validity of the intensity equation to gases, it becomes

$$A_g = (K/PL) \ln (T_0/T) y_{max} \Delta v_{\ddagger(g)} \quad \dots (7)$$

where K is a constant (1.57) for small slit widths.

The relationship of the band width in solution $\Delta y_{\ddagger(s)}$ to the band width in gas phase $\Delta y_{\ddagger(g)}$ is found from equations (1) and (7) through (3) and (6); that is,

$$\Delta y_{\ddagger(s)} = \frac{1.63 \times 10^{10}}{PL y_g} \ln (T_0/T) y_{max} \Delta y_{\ddagger(g)} \frac{(n^2+2)^2}{n} + 2.5 \text{ cm}^{-1} \quad \dots (8)$$

or

$$\Delta y_{\ddagger(s)} = 1.63 \times 10^{10} \frac{A_g (n^2+2)^2}{y_g n} + 2.5 \text{ cm}^{-1} \quad \dots (9)$$

A plot of $\Delta y_{\ddagger(s)}$ against $[(n^2+2)^2/n]$ should be a straight line. Knowing the refractive index of the solvent, frequency, maximum absorption coefficient, and band width or intensity of the gas, one can predict the band width of the solution.

RESULTS

Iogansen *et al*¹⁷ in their recent study of acetylene reported absorption data of C-H fundamental vibration in various solvents. The solution band widths in this work have been evaluated from the C-H vibration data using equation (10)

$$\Delta y_{\ddagger(s)} = 1.73 \frac{(n^2+2)^2}{n} + 2.5 \text{ cm}^{-1} \quad \dots (10)$$

which incorporates the experimentally observed value of $6.0 \times 10^7 \text{ cm}^{-3} \text{ molecule sec}$ for $\Delta y/A_s$, and the reported value of $3.6 \times 10^{-7} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ molecule}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ for A_g of the C-H stretching vibration frequency at 3289 cm^{-1} ,

Relevant results of measurement and the computed band widths are listed in Table 1 which contains solvents from inert saturated hydrocarbons to active electron donors and also includes band widths computed through equations (10) and (11), the latter being derived from Buckingham's expression (2a).

$$\Delta y_{\frac{1}{2}(s)} = 15.55 \left[\frac{9n^2}{(n^2+2)(2n^2+1)} \right] \left[1 + C'_D \frac{D-1}{2D+1} + C' \frac{n^2-1}{2n^2+1} \right] + 2.5 \text{ cm}^{-1} \quad \dots (11)$$

Values for C'_n , C'_D , refractive index factors, that is, $[9n^2/(n^2+2)(2n^2+1)]$ and $[(n^2-1)/(2n^2+1)]$ used in these computations are those given by Cole *et al.*¹

TABLE 1

Observed changes in the C-H stretching frequency and computed band widths of acetylene in solutions

Solvent	n^{18}	$\Delta y \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$A \times 10^7 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ molecule}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$	$\Delta y_{\frac{1}{2}}(\text{obs.}) \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$\Delta y_{\frac{1}{2}}(\text{cal})(9) \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$\Delta y_{\frac{1}{2}}(\text{cal})(10) \text{ cm}^{-1}$
Acetylene (gas)	—	—	3.6	—	—	—
Carb. Tetra.	1.469	26	6.5	24	23	23
Carb. disul.	1.630	34	6.2	28	26	23
Benzene	1.501	40	7.0	22	23	—
Nitrobenzene	1.382	37	8.4	21	22	—
Acetonitrile	1.346	59	8.7	33	22	28
Acetone	1.359	71	10.8	44	21	28
Dioxane	1.417	74	10.8	48	22	25

As expected of equation (6), $\Delta y/A_s$ remains almost constant, the data supporting the equation. Results presented however, are not very refined as the experimental band widths being small could vary within $\pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. In saturated hydrocarbons where the intensity and frequency are close to those for the gas the validity is good, while in active solvents of high polarity where the intensity and frequency show spectral manifestations of strong hydrogen bonding between the C-H group and solvents the deviation from observed values is noticeable: The deviation may be attributed to one of these assumptions that (1) the Chako expression is universally valid and (2) that the experimentally determined frequency shift band width relationship is of general validity.

DISCUSSION

It is to be mentioned that the equation

$$A = (K/cL) \ln (T_0/T) y_{max} \Delta y_{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots (12)$$

was applied by Ramsay¹⁶ to liquids and solutions, and values of K were calculated as a function of $\ln(T_0/T) y_{max}$ and $\Delta y_{\frac{1}{2}}$ using the assumptions (1) that the absorption band is not

overlapped and (2) that the ideal shape could be expressed by a Lorentz curve. In the use of the equation (2) it is assumed that the band considered is only the vibrational band free from any rotational interference; but it so happens that in some cases the experimental band is not free from rotational bands¹⁹. We are theoretically justified in our assumption of a true Lorentz line shape since in the absence of the rotational and other interfering bands the vibrational band could only be a true Lorentzian curve. Furthermore, since the final equation (9) does not contain the $\Delta y_{\frac{1}{2}}$ term, for purposes of calculation the nature of the experimental gaseous band whether composite or not, is of no significance.

There is some evidence in the literature that the equations of Chako, Polo and Wilson, Hirota, Buckingham and Kirkwood, Bauer and Magat do not account for the frequency shifts and intensities of the infrared bands of a given solute in a variety of solvents because of specific interactions between solute and solvent. It is perhaps because of this that the proposed band width relationship does not agree with experiment in the cases like acetonitrile, acetone and dioxane where strong interactions would be expected to occur.

Huggins and Pimental's observation of the relationship in equation (6) was derived from work on hydrogen bonding between OH group and acceptor solvents. The hydrogen bonding frequency shift-band width relationship is used here in a general way²⁰. Both the shift and band width caused by hydrogen bonding seem to be unique to this intermolecular interaction.

The quantitative prediction of the band widths appeared to be a formidable problem; in the absence of a better relationship the derived equation linking the half-width of an infrared absorption band in a solution to the half-width of the solute in the gas phase is of considerable interest and value. A review of the above results lead to the conclusion that the use of equation (8) is theoretically sound since it quantitatively accounts for the experimental observations of the half-widths in solutions containing solvents like carbon tetrachloride, carbon disulphide, benzene, and nitromethane where the bonding is less prominent. A source of the discrepancy between the calculated and observed half-widths in the case of the active solvents may be attributed to the strong hydrogen bonding between the solute and solvent molecules. The effects of strong hydrogen bonding increase with increasing dielectric constant, refractive index and strong electron donor property of the medium. Hence, the discrepancy becomes less prominent when equation (11) containing both the dielectric constant and refractive index is used in the computation.

For most C-H bonds the frequency shift for the vapour-liquid of a substance except CHCl_3 stands in the ratio of 3 : 4 in the solvents CCl_4 and CS_2 . Accordingly the vapour-liquid shifts for the C-H bond studied stand in the ratio of 3 : 4 : 4.5 : 4 : 7 : 8 : 8.5 in the solvents CCl_4 , CS_2 , C_6H_6 , $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2$, CH_3CN , CH_3COCH_3 , $\text{C}_4\text{H}_8\text{O}_2$, respectively. It may be noticed that the frequency shift is large and almost twice in the last three solvents where the deviation in band widths from the observed value is noticeable. The large shift for a weakly polar bond is primarily due to the polarizability of these compounds showing the importance of inductive forces, and the deviation may be due to the solute dipole-solvent polarizability and repulsion energy relationships, when an increased $\bar{\text{C}}-\text{H}^+$ dipole leads to an increased inductive energy or decreased electron density around H atom tending to increase the vapour-liquid shift and producing a decrease in C-H stretching constant.

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